

CLASSICA

Validating AI in classifying cancer in real-time surgery

D6.2 Communication and Dissemination Plan

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D6.2 Communication and Dissemination Plan

Executive Summary

D6.2 'Communication and Dissemination Plan' (CDP) describes the programme for communication and dissemination that will be delivered by the CLASSICA project. This deliverable outlines the key messages, target audiences, delivery channels, and metrics to assess the success of the CDP strategy.

CLASSICA's work package (WP)6, 'Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation', has three communication and dissemination objectives:

- Communicate and disseminate the project, its value, benefits, and results to specific target audiences, using tailored messages and selected channels for each audience, including: the public and media; surgeons and cancer patients; healthcare agencies and payors.
- Stimulate further research and development by other teams, building on our work.
- Create awareness of and demand for the novel results of the project, including promoting our technologies and results to potential commercial partners.

This deliverable is an output of Task 6.1 'Online Communications', Task 6.2 'Communication to surgeons and professionals', and Task 6.3 'Dissemination to research communities'. It outlines a plan that will help guide partner efforts towards appropriate, achievable, and meaningful CDP activities. In addition, the team will prepare for wide-scale replication of the developed methods post-project. This is the second deliverable from WP6.

The CDP includes Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and dissemination and communication measures already mentioned in the Description of the Action (DoA). Updates to CDP may also be expected where new opportunities arise during the course of the project, with these updates reported in the Periodic Reports.

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Table of Contents

Executive Summary	1
Table of Contents.....	2
List of Figures.....	3
List of Tables.....	3
List of acronyms, definitions, and abbreviations.....	4
1 Introduction.....	5
1.1 Introduction to CLASSICA.....	5
1.2 Communication and Dissemination Plan (CDP).....	5
2 Approach.....	6
2.1 CDP objectives.....	6
2.2 CDP approach.....	6
2.3 CDP timeline.....	7
3 Results.....	8
3.1 CLASSICA Communication and Dissemination Plan	8
3.2 Key audiences and stakeholders.....	8
3.3 Key messages	9
3.4 CLASSICA brand identity	10
3.4.1 Logo	10
3.4.2 Typography.....	13
3.4.3 Written tone	13
3.4.4 Internal templates.....	14
3.5 Funding Acknowledgement.....	15
3.6 Online communication tools	15
3.6.1 CLASSICA website	15
3.6.2 Twitter	18
3.6.3 LinkedIn	20
3.7 Communication	21
3.7.1 Communication tasks	21
3.7.2 Communication channels for the CLASSICA audience	21
3.7.3 Planned Communication Activities and KPIs.....	22
3.8 Dissemination	26
3.8.1 Dissemination task	26
3.8.2 Dissemination channels for the CLASSICA audience	26
3.8.3 Planned Dissemination Activities and KPIs.....	27
3.9 Activities already carried out	30
4 Impact & Conclusion	30

List of Figures

Figure 1 CLASSICA logo.....	11
Figure 2 CLASSICA typography in Quicksand.....	11
Figure 3 CLASSICA logo in greyscale (e.g., for watermark or on colourful background).....	11
Figure 4 Colour pallet with hexadecimal values.....	12
Figure 5 Project tagline.....	12
Figure 6 Sample logos.....	13
Figure 7 Selected fonts.....	13
Figure 8 Plenary meeting slide template.....	14
Figure 9 Deliverable template.....	14
Figure 10 CLASSICA homepage banner.....	16
Figure 11 CLASSICA homepage.....	17
Figure 12 News page.....	18
Figure 13 CLASSICA on Twitter @classicaproject.....	19
Figure 14 Twitter analytics.....	19
Figure 15 CLASSICA on LinkedIn – CLASSICA Horizon Europe.....	20

List of Tables

Table 1 CDP programme phases.....	7
Table 2 Communication Audience.....	21
Table 3 Activity table for communication and dissemination – overview.....	22
Table 4 Communication activities via the website.....	23
Table 5 Communication activities via social media channels.....	24
Table 6 Communication activities via the media.....	24
Table 7 Communication materials, including newsletters, video, digital and print materials.....	25
Table 8 Dissemination Audience.....	26
Table 9 Dissemination via peer-reviewed publications.....	27
Table 10 Dissemination via conferences.....	27
Table 11 Dissemination via training events.....	28
Table 12 Dissemination via meetings.....	28
Table 13 Dissemination through collaboration with other EU projects.....	29

List of acronyms, definitions, and abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
CA	Consortium Agreement
CDP	Communication and Dissemination Plan
CMS	Content Management System
DoA	Description of Action
DTIF	Disruptive Technologies Innovation Fund
EU	European Union
FAIR data	FAIR data meets the principles of findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability
GA	Grant Agreement
ICMJE	International Committee of Medical Journal Editors
IP	Intellectual Property
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MDR	Medical Devices Regulation
OR	Operating Room
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

1.1 Introduction to CLASSICA

The Horizon Europe CLASSICA project will deliver and clinically validate an AI-based decision support technology, which allows rapid identification of the presence and distribution of cancer tumours. Validation will be carried out across several clinics, surgical teams, and countries.

Cancer and healthy tissue have radically different local blood perfusion patterns. This perfusion can be captured using near-infrared video after systemic fluorophore (indocyanine green) injection. Analysis of the video can digitally identify regions of cancer by tracking the perfusion over the initial seconds after dye administration by comparing the fluorescence signal in these areas with those in adjacent normal tissue within the same endolaparoscopic field of view. Application of AI methods (including computer vision and machine learning techniques) has enabled this differential classification to occur in real time in the OR so that better, individualised surgical decisions can be taken during an operation.

The CLASSICA AI-based technology will assist surgeons in real time during operations by accurately identifying cancerous versus healthy tissue. During the operation, a smart camera captures the colour changes in tissue after the administration of a safe fluorescent dye. Video is processed by the AI, helping the surgeon to define excision extent. This added support, combined with the surgeon's judgement and expertise, will minimise post-surgery complications and reduce the risk of cancer recurrence in the patient.

The specific objectives of the project are to:

- Deploy and carry out clinical validation studies across five clinical settings, including Ireland, Belgium, Austria, Italy, and the Netherlands.
- Assess the usability, safety, and performance of the CLASSICA system.
- Agree on standard operating protocols for the implementation and use of the CLASSICA system.
- Develop and deliver training for the use of CLASSICA tissue classification tools during biopsy and surgery.
- Develop new guidelines to help guide the use of AI for surgical decision support.

The project builds on breakthrough by the Irish DTIF Consortium comprising UCD, RCSI and IBM Research over the last three years at the Mater Hospital regarding the use of special dyes and AI to improve outcomes in cancer surgery.

1.2 Communication and Dissemination Plan (CDP)

Awareness, communication, and dissemination activities targeting specific audiences with tailored messages will maximise the impact of the CLASSICA project. This document outlines the CLASSICA Communication and Dissemination Plan (CDP). Throughout the course of the project, CLASSICA will deliver a comprehensive programme of communication and dissemination activities aimed at the public and media (communication) and healthcare researchers, practitioners, and providers (dissemination).

2 Approach

2.1 CDP objectives

As described in DoA, the communication and dissemination focus of WP6 is to:

- Communicate and disseminate the project, its value, benefits, and results to specific target audiences, using tailored messages and selected channels for each audience, including: the public and media; surgeons and cancer patients; healthcare agencies and payors.
- Stimulate further research and development by other teams, building on our work.
- Create awareness of and demand for the novel results of the project, including promoting our technologies and results to potential commercial partners.

Communications and dissemination (WP6) are cross-cutting elements for the project and involve the contribution of every project partner. The CDP will therefore ensure that a unified and consistent approach is taken across the project, maximising the communication impact, raising awareness of how public European money is spent, engaging with stakeholders, contributing to the state of the art and making knowledge and results open to other scientists and key opinion leaders. This plan involves:

- **Communication** activities to promote the project and results.
- **Dissemination** and open science to make our results public.

Communication involves reaching multiple audiences, including citizens, the media, and other stakeholders, such as surgeons, hospital leaders, medical equipment manufacturers, and patient representatives. We will reach these audiences through media channels such as our website, social media, events, magazine articles and newsletters. These channels enable us to inform, promote and communicate our project activities and results. Communication activities have already begun, with the setup of the project website and social media channels. These are described in some depth in deliverable D6.1 'Website and Online Communications Setup Report'. At the same time, partners communicated with the media through press releases and national interviews to share the news of our project kick-off.

Dissemination involves making our results public and adhering to the open science approach, whereby we make our knowledge, results, and data open and free of charge for others. CLASSICA is 'open science by design', and we plan to share our results, data, and approach with the wider community as early as possible, subject to IP and commercialisation restraints. Project data will be shared in FAIR formats on open repositories, and software will be open-sourced. This will be described in depth in the CLASSICA 'Data Management Plan' (deliverable D2.4). Dissemination activities in the CDP include publishing results (technology, data, clinical outcomes) in conferences and scientific meetings, scientific magazines, education and training events, and collaboration with other EU-funded projects.

2.2 CDP approach

The CDP is an important tool to foster optimal engagement and collaboration with key stakeholders for the project. Communication and dissemination are managed under WP6 of the DoA, led by PT and UCD. All partners are involved in WP6, by providing essential content and feedback, reporting on project outputs from their WPs, and by taking advantage of their existing networks to promote the project and outputs. Training and education will be delivered by IRCAD, Europe's leading surgical

education organisation. Draft clinical guidelines to support surgeons in the use of CLASSICA decision-support technologies will be created by EAES and UCD for future adoption.

Communication and dissemination monitoring will occur regularly (every two weeks), whereby all partners will be asked to report on their upcoming or recent activities. Activities will be tracked in a communications and dissemination register, and news/social media items will be drafted to boost the impact of the activity. By performing regular monitoring of activities, we can determine if our action plan is being carried out correctly and on time

The CDP was adapted from the content in the DoA, in which all project partners were invited to contribute by identifying key messages, target audiences, communication channels, and related outputs. Key Performance Indicators (KPI's) will be used to track our progress on a continual basis. KPI metrics to measure success will be feasible, achievable, and measurable. This document is a practical handbook to be consulted by all partners to contribute to WP6. The CDP is a living document and will be evaluated annually by partners and amended accordingly. This will ensure that the plan remains relevant and takes advantage of new communication and dissemination opportunities. Any updates will be reported in subsequent Periodic Reports.

2.3 CDP timeline

WP6 is an overarching work package that runs for the entire duration of the project. All project partners are involved, with five phases:

Table 1 CDP programme phases

Months	CDP Programme	Outputs
M1 – M3	Strategy & Planning Initial consortium meetings CDP and timescale designed DoA informs plan	Communication and Dissemination Plan. Systems in place for internal communications (Dropbox for resource sharing, email calls for news, etc.).
M1 – M48	Awareness building Growth building Consortium meetings Materials and digital media (e.g., logo, website) prepared Dissemination to specialist audiences	Media & templates for internal communications. CLASSICA becomes known to citizens, the media, and opinion leaders. Online communications position CLASSICA as trustworthy entity that is known to stakeholders. Publication policy to guide dissemination. Dissemination audience connected.
M16 – M48	Market positioning Task force/focus group meetings with external surgeons Stakeholder conference to gather input on legal and liability	Training programmes developed. Stakeholder input on liability and legal aspects of AI-assisted surgery.

Months	CDP Programme	Outputs
	Dissemination at large symposia AI technology demonstrator Training and demonstration materials prepared Raise awareness of AI-enabled tools for better patient outcomes Engagement with regulators	Generalised AI tool implemented with substantial datasets. Video processing algorithms made freely available on GitHub. Pathway towards future regulatory approval defined. Blockers and facilitators for use of CLASSICA in the OR identified.
M30 – M48	Generation of interest Final consortium meetings to include exploitation sessions Exploitation planning and IP/Exploitation Workshops Task force/focus group for draft clinical guidelines Demonstrations enabling potential users/payors to experience CLASSICA	Exploitation Plan agreed. Recommendations to address blockers and facilitators implemented. Draft clinical guidelines made public.
M30 – M48+	Legacy phase Continuous interactions between partners and established audiences Commercialisation of the CLASSICA technology for wide-scale exploitation	High-impact publications. Future Medical Device Regulation (MDR) CE marking after project end. Formal adoption of clinical guidelines after technology brought to market and wider adoption of the programme of surgical education and training.

3 Results

3.1 CLASSICA Communication and Dissemination Plan

The CLASSICA team will promote the CLASSICA project and methods for AI-enabled fluorescence-guided surgery to relevant stakeholders at the European and global levels.

3.2 Key audiences and stakeholders

Stakeholders and potential channels were initially agreed upon in the DoA, with a basic strategic framework for reaching dissemination and communication targets agreed.

Our national, regional, and international stakeholders include both scientific and non-scientific audiences. The main audiences will be the (i) public and media,

(ii) surgeons and professionals, and (iii) research communities. Key target audiences also include the clinical community, healthcare buyers and hospitals, and surgical equipment companies towards the end of the project.

- **Communication targets:** non-specialist audiences, including the public and the media, patient organisations, cancer patients and carers, as well as specialist audiences, including surgeons and professionals, researchers, healthcare decision makers and buyers, hospitals, and professional organisations.
- **Dissemination targets:** specialist audiences including clinicians (cancer surgeons), researchers and scientists, healthcare decision makers and hospital administrators, research funders, patients, and industry.

Multipliers: Multipliers can increase the reach of CLASSICA and include specialist and non-specialist audiences. Multipliers can be social media influencers (e.g., @escp_tweets, @TAMISYoda, @WHO) and online events such as National Colorectal Cancer Awareness Month, other EU funded projects under the HORIZON-HLTH-2021-DISEASE-04-04 call, professional and representative organisations including ECPC, AMOC, and LSI, or other national initiatives. Also, multipliers include the CLASSICA team’s very own networks: for example, the global networks of all partners, particularly IRCAD and EAES.

3.3 Key messages

CLASSICA will clinically validate the use of an AI solution for the characterisation of rectal polyps for transanal minimally invasive surgery.

The following tailored messages address our target audiences:

Communication

AI in the clinic holds immense promise for all patients. New technologies are emerging to reduce patient burden and improve clinical outcomes (**Patients and the public**)

AI will facilitate better patient outcomes for cancer surgery (**The media**)

Research funding has been well invested, leading to important new technology and high-impact outputs that will make a real difference in cancer care (**Funding agencies**)

Dissemination

CLASSICA is an exciting new imaging and decision-support technology that realistically and tangibly assists surgeons to deliver better patient outcomes (**Clinicians/cancer surgeons**)

AI-powered dynamic analysis of perfusion is an important new scientific tool. CLASSICA offers powerful tools for cancer status determination (**Scientists and researchers**)

CLASSICA offers a novel technology that can deliver better cancer outcomes (**Hospital administrators and health care buyers**)

3.4 CLASSICA brand identity

The project brand identity includes the logo, typography, colour scheme, tagline, fonts used, tone of voice, as well as positioning. During the first months of CLASSICA, PT developed the following branded tools for the team based on input and suggestions received from partners at the kick-off meeting:

- Project logo with text option, with different colour variations, file formats, and resolutions for print and for the web.
- Style guide for visual identity and public-facing copy (e.g., tweets or news items on the website).
- Word template for project deliverables.
- PowerPoint template for presentations.

By using these resources and templates, the consortium will ensure that the branding is consistent throughout the project.

3.4.1 Logo

The CLASSICA logo (Figure 1), logo text element (Figure 2), and colour palette (Figure 4) were developed in the early months of the project. Multiple versions of the logo are available to the team – from low resolution to high resolution, in multiple file formats, and for digital and print. The logo is used for all CLASSICA dissemination activities.

Figure 1 CLASSICA logo

CLASSICA

Figure 2 CLASSICA typography in Quicksand

Visual style guide: The logo is an important element of the CLASSICA brand and should be used consistently and on all communication materials. The logo will most often be represented in full colour but can also be adapted to greyscale (Figure 3) as a background element. The logo should always be presented with the faces upright and facing to the left.

Figure 3 CLASSICA logo in greyscale (e.g., for watermark or on colourful background)

There should be clear space around the logo to ensure the logo does not get crowded. The logo should not be smaller than 70 px in digital material or 20 mm in print. The logo orientation should not be modified, it should not be stretched or squashed, and the colour tone should not be changed outside of the CLASSICA colour palette or greyscale.

The logo can be used in combination with the project name, 'CLASSICA' in capital letters. An image of the logo text is available (Figure 2 above), or the text can be written using Quicksand font and the navy colour in the colour palette below. When using the logo and text element, the font size should be in proportion to the logo emblem.

Figure 4 Colour pallet with hexadecimal values

Blue, orange, grey and navy act as the primary colours of the CLASSICA brand. These colours are used for headings, backgrounds, and design elements (Figure 4). Black is most often used for typography.

The project tagline - The future of AI assisted cancer surgery - is prominently displayed on the project website (Figure 5). An animated banner introduces users to the project and our ultimate impact.

Figure 5 Project tagline

Several iterations of the logo (Figure 6 below) were created before a final selection was made. The project team voted on their chosen logos and provided feedback and suggestions on how best to represent the project with a visual symbol. After several iterations, the final logo (Figure 1 above) was agreed.

Figure 6 Sample logos

3.4.2 Typography

The main font used for outward-facing materials is 'Quicksand'. This is used for headings and in the project logo. Quicksand is a sans serif font with rounded terminals. 'DM Sans' is used for the body of text on digital media and the website. DM Sans is a low-contrast sans serif font that was designed to work well at smaller text sizes. Quicksand and DM Sans are both open-source font families from the Google Fonts library. These fonts are licensed under the Open Font License¹. Fallback fonts include default sans-serif for the platform, Helvetica Neue, Helvetica, and Arial.

Quicksand DM Sans Calibri

Figure 7 Selected fonts

'Calibri' is used for scientific reporting (i.e., deliverable Word body text, PowerPoint body and list text). Calibri is the default font for these reports because it is optimised for screen display and is made available with Microsoft Office. All fonts are legible in small sizes.

3.4.3 Written tone

Written communication will be consistent across website news, social media updates, and other digital media outputs (e.g., visual abstract and flyers). The tone of written material will be serious and engaging. Content will be accessible to the public interested in new technological developments in AI and cancer, and more knowledgeable audiences with specific expertise or special interests in the project domains. Content (web copy, tweets, flyers etc.) will be simple, relevant, and useful. Content will be reinforced with evidence and will be illustrated with supporting images or other media. Technical and scientific information will be made accessible by translating it into a language that is

¹ https://scripts.sil.org/cms/scripts/page.php?site_id=nrsi&id=OFL

simple to understand. The content will be tailored to suit different audiences, ensuring that all audience types understand our core message.

3.4.4 Internal templates

In addition to public-facing materials, the team developed several internal templates to help ensure a unified and cohesive approach is taken. A PowerPoint template (Figure 8) is used for presentations at project plenary meetings. The deliverable template (Figure 9 below) is used for all project deliverables, including public and sensitive reports.

Figure 8 Plenary meeting slide template

Figure 9 Deliverable template

3.5 Funding Acknowledgement

Horizon Europe Funding will be acknowledged on all manuscripts, poster presentations and all forms of dissemination emerging from the project. The following standardised wording will be used:

"Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the Health and Digital Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them."

Alternatively, partners can use the following text where necessary:

"Co-Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the Health and Digital Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them."

In addition, partners will display the EU emblem whenever possible (i.e., poster, slides, website). When displayed together with another logo, the EU emblem must have appropriate prominence. High-resolution emblems can be found here: https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/default/files/eu-emblem-rules_en.pdf.

Bibliographic metadata must be in a standard format and must include all the following:

- the term "Horizon Europe",
- CLASSICA, grant no. 101057321,
- the publication date, and length of embargo period if applicable, and
- a persistent identifier.

These requirements are made available to partners in the CLASSICA Publication Policy. This internal policy document will be agreed upon by all partners and reported in the next Periodic Report. It will provide a quick reference guide for project partners. It outlines partners' publication rights and responsibilities and is based on the agreed mechanisms in the Grant Agreement (GA) and Consortium Agreement (CA) as well as authorship and recognition guidelines based on ICMJE.

3.6 Online communication tools

3.6.1 CLASSICA website

CLASSICA communication began at the outset of the project and will continue throughout its entire lifetime. The project website and social media channels are described in depth in deliverable D6.1' Website and Online Communications Setup Report'. The website is live at <https://classicaproject.eu/> and is illustrated in Figure 10 and Figure 11 below.

Figure 10 CLASSICA homepage banner

The purpose of the CLASSICA website is to serve as a hub for project communication and dissemination. One of the first steps in publicly communicating the project is the establishment and maintenance of the project website, with descriptions of the project objectives, team involvement, key innovations, and societal impact. The website and associated social media channels will be used to build trust between the project as a whole and individuals in our target audiences. A dedicated news section (Figure 12 below) will cover recent project news, host articles and posts dealing with different aspects of CLASSICA, news of the project or other relevant publications, and will drive traffic to the website.

Figure 11 CLASSICA homepage

Figure 12 News page

3.6.2 Twitter

Twitter is the main social media channel we will use to promote the project and our outputs. The Twitter account was set up in M1 of the project. Figure 13 below shows the Twitter account @classicaproject. The Twitter profile uses the same banner as our LinkedIn profile.

Figure 13 CLASSICA on Twitter @classicaproject

Twitter enables us to connect with our specialist and non-specialist audiences, including surgeons, other related research projects, and interested citizens who could benefit from the CLASSICA technology. The typical user who will follow the project account is knowledgeable about one or more of our subject domains but may not be an expert. Therefore, a conversational, serious, and informative communication style is preferred. Content should be short and clear, with supporting images or videos wherever possible. Regular Twitter communication will enable us to engage in a two-way conversation with our audience and will help to establish trust in the project online. Twitter users can like, retweet or reply to content.

Hashtags agreed at the plenary meeting include #CLASSICA, #colorectal, #cancer, and #AI. Other relevant hashtags can be used, and partners have been asked to tag the project @classicaproject when talking about project outputs or interesting related material.

Figure 14 Twitter analytics

Twitter analytics² will be used to measure the reach of our tweets (impressions), level of engagement, number of retweets, and follower count (as illustrated in Figure 14 above).

3.6.3 LinkedIn

The LinkedIn group 'CLASSICA Horizon Europe'³ will address a more professional audience. Initially, this includes the project team members. Once established, external experts will be invited, including actors along the value chain, such as medical device manufacturers, AI developers, legal experts, and other researchers. This will enable the promotion of CLASSICA among a broad community of professionals. A professional, serious, and informative communication style is preferred. Images and links should be included in posts, with team members and partner institutions tagged in posts where relevant.

Figure 15 CLASSICA on LinkedIn – CLASSICA Horizon Europe

² <https://analytics.twitter.com/user/classicaproject/tweets>

³ <https://www.linkedin.com/groups/14085801/>

3.7 Communication

3.7.1 Communication tasks

There are two key communication tasks in WP6:

- Online communications targeting the public and media, and
- Communication to surgeons and professionals.

These tasks will be carried out throughout the entire project and will be achieved through a number of communication activities, as outlined below.

3.7.2 Communication channels for the CLASSICA audience

The communication audience, objectives and planned communication channels are highlighted in Table 2 below. This table provides a high-level overview of how and why we will reach specific audiences. Planned communication activities and measurable indicators for their success are outlined below.

Table 2 Communication Audience

Audiences	Objectives	Communication channels
Internal Stakeholders - all consortium partners	<p>Promote cooperation and engagement between all partners.</p> <p>Develop an effective communications process between all work packages and partners within CLASSICA.</p> <p>Evolving communication methods over the course of the project.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dropbox. • Email and other written communications. • CLASSICA meetings. • Ad-hoc discussions. • Face-to-face and virtual meetings. • Website (classicaproject.eu). • Deliverables.
External Communication – public and media	<p>Raise awareness, communicate message, and share outputs with external non-specialist stakeholder audiences online.</p> <p>Show the success of European collaboration and raise awareness of how public money is spent.</p> <p>Non-specialist stakeholder Audiences: -</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Citizens • Patient organisations, cancer patients, and carers • EU Institutions • Industry (researchers and medical manufacturers) • Innovators 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website (classicaproject.eu). • Social media (#classica). • Press-releases, interviews and media articles. • EU Commission Communication Tools. • Public deliverables and reports. • Articles & additional publications. • Stakeholder conference, task force/focus group seminars.
External Communication – surgeons and professionals	<p>Raise awareness, communicate message, and share outputs with external specialist stakeholder audiences online and through a variety of professional channels.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website (classicaproject.eu). • Social media (LinkedIn). • Direct contact through task force or focus group meetings. • Bilateral industry events and direct meetings with industry.

Audiences	Objectives	Communication channels
	<p>Engage with stakeholders, validate or modify the CLASSICA approach through stakeholder feedback, generate market demand.</p> <p>Specialist stakeholder audiences: -</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU Institutions and other EU projects • Academic and Industry researchers • Surgeons and the clinical community • Investors • Local, National, Regional authorities (e.g., HPRRA, AIFA, FAGG-AFMPS) • Specific end user communities (healthcare providers, hospitals, payors, clinicians and surgeons) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presentations (PPT) at scientific and patient focused meetings. • Press-releases, interviews and media articles. • Posters. • Position/white papers. • Public deliverables and reports. • Articles & additional publications. • EU Commission Communication Tools. • Training and dissemination events. • Stakeholder conference, task force/focus group seminars. • Presentations at international conferences. • Intermediary channels such as the IRCAD newsletter, contact database. • Participation in outreach events.

3.7.3 Planned Communication Activities and KPIs

Project news, outputs, and achievements will be communicated through a variety of mechanisms by the project as a whole and from individual partners through the channels identified below. Here we outline the planned communication activities and related KPIs for each relevant communication channel. An overview of the activity table is provided in Table 3 below.

Table 3 Activity table for communication and dissemination – overview

Activity or Messages	Audience	Channel	Frequency or Date	Responsibility	Target / KPI
<p>What needs to be communicated/disseminated?</p> <p>How does this change over time as project results become available?</p>	<p>Who will be communicated with?</p>	<p>What method is used to reach this audience (e.g., web news, Twitter, publication?)</p>	<p>How often?</p> <p>What date complete?</p>	<p>Who is leading this activity?</p> <p>Who else is responsible?</p>	<p>What metric (qualitative or quantitative) is used, and how is it measured?</p>

The following measures will be used to evaluate the output of communication activities:

Communication channel: Website

The website serves as a central hub for all communications. As such, the content is tailored for consumption by the public and non-specialist audiences. Scientific and specialist content will also be provided, and where appropriate additional material will be included to support the non-specialist user (e.g., lay summaries of scientific publications).

Table 4 Communication activities via the website

Activity or Messages	Audience	Channel	Frequency or Date	Responsibility	Target / KPI
Website: Establish project website	All ⁴	Develop and launch project website www.classicaproject.eu	M3	PT leads. Inputs from all partners.	Website launched by M3.
Website: news published	All	News articles posted on the website. Analytics to monitor traffic.	On-going Two per month on average.	PT with input from all partners.	96 news articles over 48 months. Analytics shows reach of 5,000 visitors.
Website: Multilingual support on website	All	Multilingual functionality added to website and home page translated into project languages. Analytics to monitor use.	M13	PT develops. Partner from each country nominates a translator.	Analytics shows 100 visitors to these pages.
Website: public deliverables published	Research communities, clinical community, other EU projects.	Deliverable page on project website. News article to highlight new publications.	Four/five per year.	PT leads. Inputs from all partners.	19 deliverables published.

Communication channel: Social media

Social media channels include Twitter and LinkedIn (Table 5 below). These social networks have different aims, tools and targets. This approach will be reviewed at each plenary meeting, and new networks may be included where appropriate (e.g., ResearchGate to serve as a hub for project publications). Social media will help increase the project's impact by enabling us to engage in dialogue with our audience.

⁴ All = CLASSICA specialist audiences (academic and industrial researchers, surgeons and the clinical community, other EU projects, healthcare buyers and hospitals) and non-specialist audiences (general public, patient organisations, cancer patients, carers).

Table 5 Communication activities via social media channels

Activity or Messages	Audience	Channel	Frequency or Date	Responsibility	Target / KPI
Social: Setup Twitter	All	Setup Twitter account @classicaproject with project logo and header.	M1	PT leads.	Twitter launched in M1.
Social: Setup LinkedIn	All	Setup LinkedIn Group 'CLASSICA Horizon Europe' and invite project team to join.	M1	PT leads.	LinkedIn launched in M1.
Social: Update Twitter	All	Post tweets and RTs (e.g., news on website, related publications, information about the project, and RT partner tweets or related tweets).	8 per month. Stats captured (impressions, follower growth).	PT leads. Inputs from all partners.	8 tweets per month. 500 followers. 1 M impressions. Website traffic from social (50).
Social: Update LinkedIn	Professional and specialist audiences.	Posts and re-posts (e.g., sharing news from the website and re-posting related content).	2 per month. Stats captured (group members).	PT leads. Inputs from all partners.	2 posts per month. 50 members. Website traffic from social (50).

Communication channel: Press releases, interviews, and media articles

Project partners will engage with the press and popular media, as outlined in Table 6. Press releases will initially be drafted by the Coordinator and shared with the wider team so that they can be adapted and translated for national distribution. Copies of the local press releases will be published on the website. In addition, the team will engage with traditional (news, radio, TV) and digital (social media, podcasts) media to promote CLASSICA.

Table 6 Communication activities via the media

Activity or Messages	Audience	Channel	Frequency or Date	Responsibility	Target / KPI
Media: Press release at kick-off	General public and media.	Press release (drafted by UCD and adapted/translated by the wider team).	M1	UCD and all.	Copies of press releases (5).
Media: Press release during project	General public and media.	Press release.	First patient recruited. Project results towards end of project.	UCD and all.	Copies of press release (10).

Activity or Messages	Audience	Channel	Frequency or Date	Responsibility	Target / KPI
Media: News articles and interviews	General public and media.	Harness traditional media and digital media.	M1 (each research partner, once per year).	All	Copies of news articles/interview recordings (40).
Media: Periodical magazine articles	All	Articles in patient-organisation periodicals (e.g., ECPC (Europe), AMOC (Italy), LSI (Ireland), SND (NL).	M3 onwards.	All	Articles published (5).

Communication channel: Events

Several events have already been planned in the DoA. These are outlined in the dissemination section below and include education and training events (Table 11 below) and meetings with stakeholders (Table 12 below). Additional events will be added to these tables as required.

Communication channel: Newsletters, digital and print materials

The team will output digital materials, newsletters, and videos as described in Table 7 below. Given the intensely visual nature of our research, video material will be central to all our communication and dissemination activities. Video of clinical work and the technology in action will be compelling and exciting.

Table 7 Communication materials, including newsletters, video, digital and print materials

Activity or Messages	Audience	Channel	Frequency or Date	Responsibility	Target / KPI
Material: IRCAD surgical newsletter	Surgeons (400,000 subscribing surgeons worldwide).	IRCAD surgical newsletter.	Every 12 months.	IRCAD leads. Inputs from all partners.	3 articles featuring CLASSICA.
Material: Visual abstract	All	PowerPoint template illustrating the project in one slide.	M6	PT leads. Inputs from all partners.	No. of times slides are presented at events (44).
Material: Flyer	All	Printed flyer and digital version on the website.	M8 with updates made in line with project results.	PT leads. Inputs from all partners.	Project flyers printed (20 per partner). Project flyers downloaded from website (200).
Material: Video	All	Video presentations of the technology in action.	M9 with updates for each study.	UCD, IRCAD, UNITO, ZOL, VUMC, BBGRAZ, PT	No. of videos released (4). Analytics shows 1,000 views.

3.8 Dissemination

3.8.1 Dissemination task

There is one cross-cutting dissemination task in WP6:

- Dissemination to the research communities.

This task will be achieved through a number of dissemination activities, as described below.

3.8.2 Dissemination channels for the CLASSICA audience

The dissemination audience overlaps with the communication audience (Table 2 above). Table 8 illustrates our dissemination objectives and channels that will be used to reach various communities. We will make our results public and adhere to the open science approach. This means making our knowledge, results, and data open and free of charge for others. Project outputs will be *as open as possible, as closed as necessary*, ensuring that we protect IP and publications. We will generate substantial datasets from five clinical validation sites across Europe. Project data will be shared in FAIR formats on open repositories, and software will be open-sourced (c.f. the CLASSICA 'Data Management Plan', deliverable D2.4).

Table 8 Dissemination Audience

Audiences	Objectives	Dissemination channels
Dissemination – dissemination of project results	<p>Share the project results (technology, data, clinical outcomes) for others to use.</p> <p>Maximise project impact and establish CLASSICA as a prime mover in the area of AI for cancer surgery.</p> <p>Generate demand for the CLASSICA outputs by other research teams (academic or commercial).</p> <p>Scientific Audiences: -</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clinicians (cancer surgeons) • Scientists and researchers • Surgeons and the clinical community • Other EU projects and institutions <p>Industry Audiences: -</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Industry, medical manufacturers • Investors and innovators <p>Citizens and specific end-user communities: -</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patient organisations, cancer patients, carers • Healthcare providers, hospitals, payors • Local, National and Regional authorities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publications (Lancet, JAMA, BJS, AnnSurg, AIM, Open Research Europe, etc.). • Conferences and clinical congress (EAES, SAGES, ESSO, MICCAI, AMIA, etc.). • Direct contact through task force meetings or seminars with audiences via EAES or IRCAD. • EU Commission Communication Tools. • Education and training events. • Presentations (PPT) at scientific and patient-focused meetings. • Stakeholder conference, task force/focus group seminars. • Data published in open repositories in FAIR format. • Software released open source.

3.8.3 Planned Dissemination Activities and KPIs

Dissemination of the project results is an essential step to raising awareness and creating future demand for products based on CLASSICA AI technology. Here we outline the planned dissemination activities and related KPIs for each channel. We will disseminate results to the audiences that will use them, and that are most important for future commercialisation and clinical adoption.

The following measures will be used to evaluate the output of dissemination activities:

Dissemination channel: Publications

The team will ensure open access to peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to our results, as shown in Table 9. Open access will be provided, with publications deposited in a repository. In addition, publications will be made available for download on our project website. A CLASSICA Publication Policy document helps guide the team on their publication rights and responsibilities and is a quick-reference guide for the agreed mechanisms in the GA and CA.

Table 9 Dissemination via peer-reviewed publications

Activity or Messages	Audience	Channel	Frequency or Date	Responsibility	Target / KPI
Publication: Journal articles	Surgery, cancer, technology, AI Ethics and law of AI.	Publications such as Lancet, JAMA, Annals of Surgery, British Journal of Surgery.	Four publications.	All	No. of journal articles (4).
Publication: Conference proceedings	Clinicians, scientists, researchers.	Conferences and clinical congress proceedings such as EAES, SAGES, ASCO, ESSO, MICCAI, AMIA.	10 publications.	All	No. of publications (10). Size of audience/reach (300).

Dissemination channel: Conferences

Conferences will enable us to share how CLASSICA is a clear and tangible demonstration of the real-world value of AI in the surgical context. We will raise awareness and appreciation of AI-enabled tools, leading to better acceptance and adoption. Project partners will disseminate via conferences, as outlined in Table 10.

Table 10 Dissemination via conferences

Activity or Messages	Audience	Channel	Frequency or Date	Responsibility	Target / KPI
Conference: Participation at a conference	Clinicians, scientists, researchers.	Presentation, invited talk, poster presentation.	M12 onwards.	All research partners.	No. of presentations/posters (5). Size of audience/reach (150).

Activity or Messages	Audience	Channel	Frequency or Date	Responsibility	Target / KPI
		Conferences and clinical congresses such as EAES, SAGES, ASCO, ESSO, MICCAI, AMIA.			
Conference: Participation at a workshop	Clinicians, scientists, researchers.	Participation at a workshop.	M12 onwards.	All research partners.	No. of presentations/posters (5). Size of audience/reach (150).

Dissemination channel: Education and training events

Multiple education and training events are planned within CLASSICA. In addition, two public masterclass symposia will invite external surgeons (Table 11). These events will provide us with crucial feedback on barriers and facilitators to the adoption of the CLASSICA technology. Additional education events will be added to this table as required.

Table 11 Dissemination via education events

Activity or Messages	Audience	Channel	Frequency or Date	Responsibility	Target / KPI
Education: Masterclass symposia	Surgeons, and other external experts, including healthcare providers, AI researchers, legal experts, and training experts.	Masterclass as part of large symposia meeting.	Two editions.	EAES	200 attendees. Audience feedback.

Dissemination channel: Meetings

Several meetings have already been planned in the DoA. These are outlined in Table 12 below. Additional meetings will be added to this table as required.

Table 12 Dissemination via meetings

Activity or Messages	Audience	Channel	Frequency or Date	Responsibility	Target / KPI
Meeting: Stakeholder Conference	Surgeons, hospital leaders, medical manufacturers, patient representatives.	UCPH hosts stakeholder conference.	One meeting.	UCPH, PSU	No. of people reached (40). Audience feedback.

Activity or Messages	Audience	Channel	Frequency or Date	Responsibility	Target / KPI
Meeting: Task Force/Focus Group	Surgeons (EAES member-surgeons in related fields).	EAES task force meetings.	4 meetings.	EAES	6 external experts per meeting. Audience feedback.
Meeting: Seminars at each clinical site	Surgeons and patient organisations.	Seminar includes demonstration and video presentation of CLASSICA in action.	Two per country.	UCD, UNITO, ZOL, VUMC, BBGRAZ	No. of people reached (100). Audience feedback.

Dissemination channel: Collaboration with other EU-funded projects

Collaboration with other EU-funded projects, including other projects funded under the same Horizon Europe funding call (HORIZON-HLTH-2021-DISEASE-04-04), is illustrated in Table 13. Joint meetings will enable us to discuss dissemination and collaboration as well as common regulatory and clinical evaluation concerns.

Table 13 Dissemination through collaboration with other EU projects

Activity or Messages	Audience	Channel	Frequency or Date	Responsibility	Target / KPI
EU: Collaboration with projects under HORIZON-HLTH-2021-DISEASE-04-04	Other EU funded projects under the same call.	Website, joint events, social media.	At least one joint meeting. Bi-monthly interaction on social networks.	PT leads. Inputs from all partners.	No. projects promoted on website (5). No. joint events (1). No. social network interactions (1,000 impressions).
EU: Joint events with researchers in related EU projects	Scientific and clinical communities.	Joint event with researchers in related EU projects.	At least one joint meeting.	UCD, EAES, IRCAD, PT. Inputs from all partners.	No. joint events (1). Audience feedback.

3.9 Activities already carried out

- ✓ The website was launched at www.classicaproject.eu.
- ✓ The logo, colour palette, and brand have been established.
- ✓ Social networks were set up on Twitter @classicaproject and LinkedIn 'CLASSICA Horizon Europe'.
- ✓ General and local press releases were issued in the opening months of the project to advertise the launch and mission of CLASSICA.

4 Impact & Conclusion

This report describes the CLASSICA Communication and Dissemination Plan. It outlines a plan that will help guide partner efforts towards appropriate, achievable, and meaningful CDP activities. It does this by outlining the planned communication and dissemination activities, channels to reach target audiences, tailored messages for the CLASSICA target audiences, and indicators of success. It will ensure we deliver clear and relevant project-related information to citizens and specialist audiences. This guidance will help the CLASSICA team to communicate and disseminate with a unified approach. The CDP will be reviewed periodically, with updates and KPIs reported in Periodic Reports.